

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

Artificial intelligence for climate prediction of extremes: State of the art, challenges, and future perspectives

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Abstract

Extreme events such as heat waves and cold spells, droughts, heavy rain, and storms are particularly challenging to predict accurately due to their rarity and chaotic nature, and because of model limitations. However, recent studies have shown that there might be systemic predictability that is not being leveraged, whose exploitation could meet the need for reliable predictions of aggregated extreme weather measures on timescales from weeks to decades ahead. Recently, numerous studies have been devoted to the use of artificial intelligence (AI) to study predictability and make climate predictions. AI techniques have shown great potential to improve the prediction of extreme events and uncover their links to large-scale and local drivers. Machine and deep learning have been explored to enhance prediction, while causal discovery and explainable AI have been tested to improve our understanding of the processes underlying predictability. Hybrid predictions combining AI, which can reveal unknown spatiotemporal connections from data, with climate models that provide the theoretical foundation and interpretability of the physical world, have shown that improving prediction skills of extremes on climate-relevant timescales is possible. However, numerous challenges persist in various aspects, including data curation, model uncertainty, generalizability, reproducibility of methods, and workflows. This review aims at overviewing achievements and

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challenges in the use of AI techniques to improve the prediction of extremes at the subseasonal to decadal timescale. A few best practices are identified to increase trust in these novel techniques, and future perspectives are envisaged for further scientific development.

This article is categorized under:

Climate Models and Modeling > Knowledge Generation with Models

The Social Status of Climate Change Knowledge > Climate Science and Decision Making

KEYWORDS

artificial intelligence, climate extreme events, climate forecasting, hybrid modeling, subseasonal to decadal

1 | INTRODUCTION

Weather and climate extremes strongly affect many aspects of our society and the natural environment. Being an intrinsic part of a changing climate, there is extensive evidence that the probability and intensity of extreme events have increased and will continue to do so in a warming world (AghaKouchak et al., 2020; Alexander et al., 2006; Orłowsky & Seneviratne, 2012). Therefore, policy-makers and stakeholders urgently need reliable predictions of occurrence probabilities or other aggregated measures of extreme weather on timescales from days to decades. However, the predictive skill of extreme events remains limited, despite recent advancements in weather and climate prediction systems.

Challenges are multiple:

- The anthropogenic climate forcing has accelerated since the beginning of the 21st century, mainly due to growing global economy and reduced absorbing efficiency of land and ocean CO₂ sinks (Canadell et al., 2007). Studies based on an older attribution period frequently underestimate the effect of global warming on the probability of unprecedented recent extremes, reflecting the difference between frequencies during the attribution period and out-of-sample verification period (Diffenbaugh, 2020).
- The physical processes driving the occurrence of extreme events differ among timescales, posing unique research questions, and requiring distinct definitions of the event to understand the underlying mechanisms.
- The number of past extreme events is intrinsically small and many may be overlooked due to scarcity of the observation availability (Seneviratne et al., 2021). Therefore, ensembles of dynamical models are often entrusted with the detection and attribution of their drivers, with possible misinterpretations caused by model limitations.
- Poor representation of key processes and feedback mechanisms in state-of-the-art numerical climate models, combined with uncertainties in the initial state, complicates predictions in a complex, and chaotic system like the atmosphere (Faranda et al., 2017).

To face these challenges, the international scientific community has made important steps in the last two decades. On the one hand, the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) has launched initiatives on near-term climate prediction within the new-born Earth System Modeling core project (<https://www.wcrp-climate.org/esmo-overview>), like the Lighthouse activity on Explaining and Predicting Earth System Change (EPESC; Findell et al., 2021; see <https://www.wcrp-climate.org/epesc>). These initiatives aim at developing numerical experiments for subseasonal-to-interdecadal variability, predictability, and predictions, and at delivering, a quantitative understanding of the changes spanning the Earth system through process-based detection and attribution.

Additionally, significant advancements in Earth observation technologies have enhanced the accuracy and scope of collected data (Board, 2019; Guo et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2022). The launch of the EU Copernicus program, the world's most ambitious program on Earth Observation, the deployment of new satellite systems and sensors (e.g., MODIS, Sentinel) providing high-resolution images of the Earth's surface, and an increasing collaboration between regional space agencies have boosted available information.

This era of “big data” has, in turn, fueled the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in many domains of Earth science (Boukabara et al., 2021; Huntingford et al., 2019; Irrgang et al., 2021; Reichstein et al., 2019; Sun et al., 2022). AI here refers to any methodology, including machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL), in which machines emulate human intelligence to solve tasks based on available data. AI algorithms can learn nonlinear relationships between input and output or to extract spatial and temporal patterns from massive datasets, without prior knowledge of the underlying Earth system processes and dynamics. This makes AI particularly useful for applications lacking have a complete theory. For instance, AI can explore subtle or hidden linkages among Earth system's variables, to uncover relevant processes not yet implemented in physically based models. Additional benefits include AI's flexibility to employ a wider range of input variables, such as novel remote sensing observations, as opposed to physics-based models that use traditionally assumed correlated input variables. AI can thus help exploit the full potential of big data, leading to new insights into Earth system processes that can inform model development and evaluation.

Progress in AI-based forecasting on weather timescales, that is, less than 10 days, has been remarkable in the last few years. In parallel with the rapid rise of AI, forecasting institutes worldwide and Big Tech companies have seized upon the opportunity to improve weather forecasts, gaining skills comparable to that of state-of-the-art dynamical predictions (Bi et al., 2023; Keisler, 2022; Lam et al., 2022; Pathak et al., 2022), even for unprecedented extreme events (Pasche et al., 2024). Recently, a cascade ML system has surpassed the ECMWF high-resolution forecast on a 15-day lead time (Chen et al., 2023).

TABLE 1 List of acronyms often used in this article.

	Acronym	Extended name
Climate	AMV	Atlantic multidecadal variability
	ENSO	El Niño southern oscillation
	MJO	Madden Julian oscillation
	PDO	Pacific decadal oscillation
	QBO	Quasi-Biennial oscillation
	S2D	Subseasonal to decadal
	S2S	Subseasonal to seasonal
	SPI	Standardized precipitation index
	SSW	Sudden stratospheric warming
	Algorithms	ANN
CNN		Convolutional neural network
ELM		Extreme learning machine
GAN		Generative adversarial model
LSTM		Long short-term memory
FS		Feature selection
RF		Random forest
SVR		Support vector regression
XAI		eXplainable artificial intelligence
XGBoost	eXtreme gradient boosting	
Metrics	BSS	Brier skill score
	CSI	Critical score index
	MAE	Mean absolute value
	MCC	Matthews correlation coefficient
	ROC	Relative operating characteristics
	RMSE	Root mean square error
	RPSS	Ranked probability skill score

Compared to the short timescales, progress on the subseasonal to decadal (S2D) timescale has been less striking. A fundamental challenge is the limited amount of independent training data, roughly one or two orders of magnitude smaller than for weather timescales. In fact, weather predictions may target individual extreme events, while climate prediction can only aggregate events over time (Meehl et al., 2021), making the number of past observational samples inevitably smaller for climate predictions. This has hampered the development of long-lead forecasts of extremes like drought and warm spells, which likely have some predictability at the S2D scale. The predictability of the climate system beyond the deterministic timescale may be greater than current CMIP6 climate models suggest (Scaife & Smith, 2018; Smith et al., 2019). In fact, an increasing number of articles has been published since the “S2S reboot” opinion paper (Cohen et al., 2019), that claimed that ML techniques developed in computer science could increase the accuracy of predictions at subseasonal to seasonal (S2S) scale.

So far, the development of AI methods for the prediction of extreme events has been overlooked, despite their critical applications and usefulness in real life (Watson, 2022). A recent review (Salcedo-Sanz et al., 2024) addressed the problem of AI for extreme events in terms of attribution, characterization, and prediction, with detailed information on applicable algorithms. Olivetti and Messori (2024) have recently published a perspective paper on the role of DL in weather predictions.

The present survey explores AI's potential to improve the prediction of extremes at the S2D timescale, and to reveal their links to large-scale and local drivers. By reviewing recent literature on AI applications for climate predictions of extreme events and the prospects brought by the combination of empirical and dynamical methods, it discusses the challenges of the data-driven approach and future perspectives, providing climate scientists with a state-of-the-art framework available for rigorous future applications.

Given the frequent appeal to acronyms for climate modes of variability and AI algorithms, we summarize and define those recurrently used in this article in Table 1.

2 | PREDICTION AND PREDICTABILITY OF EXTREME EVENTS AT SEASONAL TO DECADEAL TIMESCALES

2.1 | Definitions of extreme events and their prediction beyond the weather timescale

An event is generally considered extreme if the value of a variable exceeds (or lies below) a given threshold, which can be defined in different ways to focus on specific aspects of the extremes and meet application needs. For example, one definition counts the number of days where temperature, precipitation, etc. exceeds a relative threshold, such as the daily 90th or 99th percentile over a reference period. This can occur at any time of the year, with different seasonal impacts. It is also possible to count events that exceed an absolute threshold, like 35°C, or 50 mm/h of rain, focusing on specific impacts such as health or flood risk. These definitions are standardized in Climpact (<https://climpact-sci.org/indices/>), a widely used set of indices for identifying and comparing extreme events.

More complex definitions of extremes are based on Extreme Value Theory (EVT; Coles et al., 2001), which differs from methods considering only values exceeding a certain threshold in aiming at fitting extreme values into statistical distributions. The Generalized Pareto Distribution (GPD) and the Generalized Extreme Value (GEV) distribution are the main families that provide information about the probability density function of the extreme values. Both downsize the original time-series to only select extreme data-points. GPD relies on the Peak Over Threshold approach, selecting points exceeding a high threshold as extremes (e.g., Roth et al., 2014; Yiou et al., 2008), while GEV uses the Block Maxima approach, which divides data into temporal blocks (e.g., months or years) to obtain the maximum of each block (e.g., Ben Alaya et al., 2020; Russell & Huang, 2021). A typical application of EVT is to compute return levels of a meteorological events like high precipitation, wind-speed, and temperatures (e.g., Ban et al., 2020; Parey et al., 2019; Zahid et al., 2017).

Extreme weather events development depends on a favorable initial state, the presence of large-scale drivers, positive feedback, and stochastic processes (Sillmann et al., 2017). What marks the distinction between a climate prediction and a weather prediction of these events is the timescale: while specific weather predictions can be made up to 10–15 days in advance, weather as such becomes deterministically unpredictable beyond this time scale (Lorenz, 1969, 1982). Few days ahead of the occurrence of an extreme weather event, it is possible to make predictions of its occurrence and amplitude, with considerable detail about its location, onset, and duration, if the local and remote processes leading to its generation are properly initialized and well predicted (Domeisen et al., 2023). Deterministic forecasts can

be made up to 10 days ahead for specific extremes linked with long-lasting atmospheric patterns (e.g., heatwaves; Fragkoulidis et al., 2018).

Climate predictions target longer forecast times (seasons, years, or decades) and are necessarily probabilistic, predicting tendencies of the climate system rather than individual events (Meehl et al., 2021). Beyond the deterministic predictability limit, forecasts include probability distributions of the intensity and duration of extremes (Domeisen et al., 2022), temporal propensity of their occurrence (Prodhomme et al., 2022), or change in their frequency (Delgado-Torres et al., 2023). These characteristics are those potentially captured by a climate prediction of extremes (Figure 1): therefore, in this review, a climate extreme is defined as a temporal aggregation (from weeks to several years) of specific characteristics of an extreme event, like frequency, intensity, and duration. Deterministic weather forecasts will not be discussed since the scientific questions and the approaches to fulfill them can differ.

Verifying predictions of climate extremes at the S2D scale requires metrics beyond the classical anomaly correlation coefficient or root mean squared error (ACC and RMSE, respectively; Wilks, 2011), which may fail to depict the complexity of the phenomena by only considering the “predictable signal” (i.e., the ensemble mean; Kharin & Zwiers, 2002).

Rarity of sample events introduces sampling uncertainty in verification statistics (Casati et al., 2008). By definition, a climate extreme does not happen frequently, and correctly forecasting that an extreme will not occur is often considered a success. On the other hand, a correct forecast of nonoccurrence is easier to achieve than a forecast of occurrence (Jolliffe & Stephenson, 2012), and this should be accounted for in categorical scores. For instance, the Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC; Matthews, 1975) produces a high score only if the prediction is good in all the four confusion matrix categories, accounting for the imbalance between class sizes. The critical score index (CSI) is independent of the number of correct forecasts of nonevents, therefore it has often been used for this task (Schaefer, 1990). A different but related measure of extreme forecast quality is discrimination, visualized by the area below the relative operating characteristic (ROC; Mason & Graham, 2002), whose associated score indicates the forecast’s ability to correctly anticipate the

FIGURE 1 Schematic representation of the AI-based climate prediction function. Y represents the *predictand* or *target*, that is a measure of certain aspects characterizing the extremes of interest (e.g., intensity, frequency, etc.). X_{preds} are the *predictors*, such as modes of variability, or variables describing the state of an Earth System component that affects the troposphere, where the extreme takes place (illustrated as the circle at the center of the figure). These predictors act on the troposphere at different timescales: Sub-days to several days for meteorological drivers (light blue), weeks to ~2 months for land surface drivers (green), weeks to multi-years for stratospheric drivers (gray), months to decades for ocean drivers (dark blue). θ represents the *parameters* of the AI algorithm used to train the model (f).

occurrence or non-occurrence of a predefined event. Reliability and resolution are assessed by metrics like the Brier and the ranked probability skill scores (BSS; Brier, 1950; RPSS, Epstein, 1969), that use the entire forecast ensemble to predict the likelihood of an aggregated period (e.g., a season or many years) exceeding a certain extreme threshold (e.g., Delgado-Torres et al., 2023; Torralba et al., 2024). A shortcoming of categorical metrics is that rarity can lead to small or zero counts of extremes, and statistical methods to deal with such sparseness may not be always effective (Agresti, 2002).

The recent adoption of AI for extreme predictions has made common metrics often insufficient for human interpretation of results. Climate scientists generally use ML models as black boxes with no understanding of the model learning process and the justifications behind its decisions, making interpretability an important passage between model verification and the decision based on model's prediction. The interpretability tool mainly used in climate science is SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations; Lundberg & Lee, 2017), which assigns each feature of the ML/DL model an importance score, ultimately creating a ranking of importance among features.

2.2 | Predictability at different timescales

On (multi-)weekly to decadal timescales, both local and remote physical processes can contribute to the predictability of climate extremes (Figure 1). These mechanisms act seamlessly across timescales, but their relative contribution varies across forecast times and relates to the degree and timescale of interaction between the troposphere (target of this review) and the slower-evolving climate components (Mariotti et al., 2018).

In general, land–atmosphere coupled processes convey predictability over weeks to a few months, primarily modulating the occurrence, duration, and intensity of droughts and heat waves (Materia et al., 2022; Miralles et al., 2019). Stratospheric variability and stratosphere–troposphere coupling provide potential predictability from subseasonal to multi-annual timescales (Scaife et al., 2022 and references therein). For example, sudden stratospheric warmings may influence the tropospheric midlatitude jet stream (Kidston et al., 2015) for many weeks, causing, prolonged cold extremes (Domeisen et al., 2020), while the teleconnection between the QBO and northern hemisphere circulation has shown to affect precipitation amounts in the western Pacific on multi-annual scale (Gray et al., 2018). Ocean–atmosphere coupled mechanisms act on a wide range of timescales, from weeks to multiple years (see Santoso et al., 2017 for extreme ENSO events; Hardiman et al., 2020 for S2S drivers of record warm European winters, Ding et al., 2022 for multi-year predictability of ENSO warm/cold phases), while the effects of slow modes such as the Atlantic Multi-decadal Variability span decades (Zhang et al., 2019).

These variations and their interlinks with the troposphere act as boundary conditions for the atmospheric circulation (Shukla, 1998), contributing to oscillations like MJO (Zhang, 2005; Zhang et al., 2020) or ENSO (Capotondi et al., 2015; Rasmusson & Wallace, 1983), and patterns like blocking and quasi-stationary waves (Reinhold & Pierrehumbert, 1982), able to give the atmosphere persistence characteristics.

These modes of variability and couplings drive the insurgence of climate extremes, with different timescales potentially interfering with each other and affecting the amplitude and characteristics of extremes. For example, a negative PDO phase is associated with prolonged wet phases in the southeastern US winter (Fuentes-Franco et al., 2016). Seasonal damp anomalies are often reduced during El Niño years, while they are reinforced in winters marked by La Niña (Wang et al., 2014). However, during a phase of an active MJO, the extratropical response can amplify or mask the interannual ENSO signal for a few weeks in the southeastern US, potentially resulting in precipitation extremes of the opposite sign than anticipated by the ENSO phase (Arcodia et al., 2020).

Initialization with observed climate conditions allows coupled climate models to capture mechanisms of internally generated climate variations. Large trends in boundary conditions, such as greenhouse gases and aerosols, may also represent a source of predictability (Meehl et al., 2009) increasingly important with longer lead times, with the impact of background warming becoming evident in decadal predictions (Bellucci et al., 2015; Smith et al., 2019). However, the contribution of trends to predictability is also detected at subseasonal and seasonal timescales (Butler et al., 2019; Patterson et al., 2022; Wulff et al., 2022), particularly in summer when year-to-year variability is lower, potentially increasing the skill of extremes forecasts (Prodhomme et al., 2022).

AI has significant potential to enhance the predictive skill of climate extremes across timescales, possibly advancing our scientific understanding and societal preparedness (Huntingford et al., 2019). Sophisticated data-driven approaches offer the opportunity to harness the interconnections of climate drivers and processes, including local and remote interactions, stratosphere–troposphere couplings, and ocean–atmosphere interactions (see Figure 1). AI algorithms can

effectively analyze vast climate data and identify complex patterns that influence extreme events nonlinearly, without using potentially biased numerical Earth system models. Moreover, methods of explainable AI and causal discovery algorithms (e.g., Lundberg & Lee, 2017; Section 2.1) can elucidate the relative contribution of various climate drivers, such as PDO, ENSO, and the AMV, and their interaction in modulating climate extremes.

3 | AI-BASED PREDICTIONS OF CLIMATE EXTREMES: AN OVERVIEW

We overview the three main families of climate extremes holding predictability at the S2D timescale: extreme temperatures (heat waves and cold spells), droughts, and cyclones (storms and heavy rains). The use of different AI approaches and meteorological datasets, the lack of well-established benchmarks, the specificity in the definition of extremes, and the geographical variability of the applications, make a systematic comparison of the different studies virtually impossible. Many examples of extremes predicted using ML/DL algorithms are discussed in this section and summarized in Table 2, together with an overview of the perspective of combining AI with numerical models in a so-called hybrid approach.

3.1 | Extreme temperatures

Hot extremes are becoming more frequent, intense, and longer because of anthropogenic climate change (Dunn et al., 2020), with heatwaves being their most common manifestation (Barriopedro et al., 2023; Thompson et al., 2023). Cold spells are expected to become less frequent, durable, and intense in a warming world, but still pose significant challenges especially in the northern mid-latitudes during boreal winter (Matthias & Kretschmer, 2020; Tomassini et al., 2012).

Classifying temperature extremes can be challenging, since definitions differ according to the specific scientific questions, sectoral application, and timescale. Temperature extremes are often detected as (consecutive) days exceeding a certain threshold (e.g., Perkins & Alexander, 2013; Russo et al., 2014; Sillmann et al., 2013), but approaches based on cumulative metrics, are also used (Russo & Domeisen, 2023). Extreme indices cover a wide range of attributes, such as amplitude, intensity, duration, and frequency (Zhang et al., 2011), but defining extreme events is complicated when linked to climate predictions, since definitions are on one hand related to impacts, on the other hand, limited by S2D predictability. Prodhomme et al. (2022) introduced the concept of *heat wave propensity* to assess the predisposition of a season to heat waves, claiming that a seasonal forecast may more easily predict such a characteristic. Ragone et al. (2018) used a definition that merges temperature and geopotential height anomalies to detect long-lasting heat waves as temporal and spatial averages, improving the statistics of extremely rare events (Ragone & Bouchet, 2021).

AI's ability to forecast various aspects of temperature extremes on S2D timescale is demonstrated in several studies using various methods. Decision-tree-based ensemble methods like RF and XGBoost (He et al., 2021; Kiefer et al., 2023; van Straaten et al., 2022; Weirich-Benet et al., 2023) are often chosen for their robustness against overfitting. He et al. (2021), found that a simpler XGBoost trained on both reanalysis and observational data compares favorably to DL methods, outperforming climatology and least square models based on climate indices and persistence of previous weeks' anomalies. The presence of a well-defined test set and out-of-a-bag cross-validation provides a comprehensive benchmark for the comparison of AI methods for subseasonal forecasts, although stricter definitions of extremes are needed. van Straaten et al. (2022) and Kiefer et al. (2023) used RFs with explainability tools to investigate the influence of atmospheric, oceanic, and land surface states on the occurrence of heat and cold extremes. AI algorithms learn from data relationships that are either well-known or have traditionally not been considered part of the relevant processes and outperform climatology and the background trend. However, the lack of an out-of-sample test set makes results sensitive to possible overfitting. A clear distinction between validation and test is present in Weirich-Benet et al. (2023), whose RF outperforms persistence and climatology up to 6 weeks ahead of a heatwave, competing well with the ECMWF dynamical forecast.

Neural networks (NN) like CNNs, LSTMs, and transformers benefit from directly taking in spatiotemporal information (Jacques-Dumas et al., 2022; Miloshevich et al., 2023). Given the limited occurrence of extreme temperature events in historical data, NNs are often trained on data from numerical climate model simulations (Chattopadhyay et al., 2020). Given the imbalance between extremes and nonextremes, many studies undersampled the training set using only a fraction of the nonheatwave samples. Jacques-Dumas et al. (2022) achieve relevant forecast quality for

TABLE 2 List of publications using AI for the predictions of extremes at the S2D timescale.

Type of extreme	Reference (timescale)	AI methods	Datasets	Benchmark and metrics
Heat extreme	Ham et al., 2019 (Multiseasonal)	CNN	Large ensemble of CMIP5 historical runs and reanalysis Training: >100 model and reanalysis years Validation/test: reanalysis 1976–2017	Initialized climate model ACC
	He et al., 2021 (Subseasonal)	Multitask FS K-nearest neighbor Lasso regression XGBoost CNN-LSTM	Daily observations Training 1986–2016 5-day CV over the last 5 years Test: 2017–2018	Reanalysis climatology Spatial cosine similarity
	Jacques-Dumas et al., 2022 (Subseasonal)	CNN, Transfer learning	Multi-daily climate model outputs for the summer months Training: 900 model years Test: 100 model years	No benchmark provided MCC for different levels of heat extremes magnitude
	Kiefer et al., 2023 (Subseasonal)	RF + shap XAI; QRF + shap XAI	Daily Nov-Apr temperature observations from 1950 to 2020. Training: every year until 2000 and each year excluding the predicted year from 2001 to 2020	Reanalysis climatological ensemble CRPSS, BSS
	Lopez-Gomez et al., 2023 (Subseasonal)	CNN	All days from 43 years of reanalysis. Training: 34 years Validation: 4 years Test: 5 years	Persistence; initialized model prediction Categorical scores
	Miloshevich et al., 2023 (Seasonal)	CNN	Dynamical model of 8000 years Stratified 10-fold cross-validation	Model climatology
	Pyrina et al., 2021	Multilinear regression based on PCA and CCA	Several reanalysis/observational products Training ~60 years Test ~30 years	Reanalysis of persistence and climatology ACC
	Polkova et al., 2021 (Subseasonal to seasonal)	NN + causality algorithm (Causal Effect Network)	Reanalysis 10-day averages over the winter period Training ~32 years Test ~8 years	Initialized climate model ACC, ROC
	Trenary & DelSole, 2023 (Subseasonal)	Laplacian eigenvectors + Lasso	Dynamical model(s) 3000 years Reanalysis	Climatology, ENSO regression
	Van Straaten et al., 2022 (Subseasonal)	RF + shap XAI	Reanalysis Training and test: 1981–2019, 5-fold CV	Reanalysis climatology; Trend BSS
Weirich-Benet et al., 2023 (Subseasonal)	RF + linear model	Weekly observation and reanalysis. Training: 1981–2000 Validation: 2001–2009 Test: 2010–2018	Initialized climate model; persistence, climatology Categorical scores, BSS and RMSE	
Droughts	Danandeh Mehr et al., 2022 (Subseasonal)	ANN, CNN, LSTM, CNN-LSTM	Observation during 45 years (1971–2016), 70/30 training and test	Statistics scores including RMSE, MAE, Nash-Sutcliffe coeff.
	Deo and Şahin (2015)	ELM	Monthly historical observations (1958–2008 for training, 2009–2011 for testing)	ANN MAE, RMSE, Coeff of Determination, Willmott Index

TABLE 2 (Continued)

Type of extreme	Reference (timescale)	AI methods	Datasets	Benchmark and metrics
	Dikshit et al., 2021 (Subseasonal to seasonal)	LSTM	Gridded observations during 120 years (1901–2018) 85/15 training and test	No benchmark specified ROC score, MAE, RMSE, R2 over observations
	Dikshit & Pradhan, 2021 (Seasonal)	LSTM + XAI	Observations during 120 years (1901–2018) 85/15 training and test	No benchmark provided RMSE, R2, Nash-Sutcliffe coeff.
	Felsche & Ludwig, 2021 (Subseasonal)	ANN + XAI	Regional climate model, 50 ens members Training: 42 years (2150 samples) Test: 6 years	Model generated droughts Simple counting of model drought
	Li et al., 2021 (Subseasonal to seasonal)	RF, SVR, ELM	Monthly observations 30 moving training periods of 88 years for 30 sample tests	Comparison of the three ML methods BS and BSS
	Mokhtarzad et al., 2017 (Seasonal)	ANN, ANFIS, SVM	~30 years of meteorological observations (1984–2012) 85/15 training/test	Observed SPI R, RMSE, and cumulative distribution function
	Poornima & Pushpalatha, 2019 (Seasonal)	LSTM	Reanalysis daily data Training 55 years Test 1 year	No benchmark provided RMSE, mean absolute error, R2 (unclear observational ground)
	Raza et al., 2022 (Seasonal)	ELM, multi-layer perceptron	Monthly observation Training 1951–2013 Test 2014–2016	Autoregressive moving average RMSE, MAE, Willmott index, Pearson correlation
	Rhee & Im, 2017 (Subseasonal to seasonal)	DT, RF, Extremely randomized trees	Observation, remote sensing data, model forecast data (2003–2015), leave-1 year-out cross-validation	Climatology; Numerical forecasts Accuracy measure for drought category classification
	Sahoo et al., 2019 (Subseasonal)	LSTM-RNN, RNN	Observation during 50 years (1971–2020)	Persistence RMSE, Efficiency coefficient, R, MAE
	Zhang et al., 2019 (Seasonal)	XGBoost; ANN	Observations during ~60 years (1961–2017) Training/test in a 10-fold cross-validation	Distributed lag nonlinear model Cross-validated R2, RMSE, MAE
	Fu et al., 2023 (Seasonal)	CNN; Transfer learning	CESM climate simulations, HighResMIP simulations, ERA5 reanalysis ~3000 years for NH ~1500 years for SH	Initialized seasonal forecasts Simple count of the seasonal number of cyclones in comparison to observations
Storms and heavy precipitation	Polkova et al., 2021 (Subseasonal to seasonal)	NN + causality algorithm (Causal Effect Network)	Reanalysis 10-day averages over the winter period Training ~32 years Test ~8 years	Initialized climate model BSS, ROC, ACC
	Richman et al. (2017) (Seasonal)	SVR	Observations 1984–2015	Statistical model TCs count, MAE, RMSEt
	Scheuerer et al., 2020 (Subseasonal)	ANN/CNN	Weekly precipitation amounts over 20 cool seasons Training: 19*61 samples (LOOCV) Test: 1*61 samples	Empirically corrected initialized forecast RPSS

(Continues)

TABLE 2 (Continued)

Type of extreme	Reference (timescale)	AI methods	Datasets	Benchmark and metrics
	Tan et al., 2018 (Seasonal)	RF + Lasso	Reanalysis Training: 1978–2011 Test: 2012–2016	Lasso + RF with no feature selection, MLR MAE, R2
	Vosper et al., 2023	GAN	IBTrACS + MSWEP	Bilinear interpolation of low-resolution data
	Zhang et al., 2023	RF	NASA's Goddard Earth Observation System model version five (GEOS5)	Observed precipitation on regular grid (PRISM precipitation dataset)

long-lasting heatwaves, although the lack of a generalizability test makes their result conditional on the model output used for training. Miloshevich et al. (2023) extensively discuss the problem of data scarcity when predicting extremes, and show significant forecast skill for heatwaves in France, identifying in a combination between geopotential and soil moisture as the best predictor. Their results might be even undermined by the lack of ocean drivers, whose initial state is known to impart predictability at monthly and longer timescales. Lopez-Gomez et al. (2023), instead, use all the available information without explicit undersampling, finding that their NN architecture performs better than ECMWF's forecast system for extremely hot days beyond the 2-week forecast time.

Multiple linear regression approaches with tailored filtering procedures also show success (Miller & Wang, 2019; Pyrina et al., 2021; Trenary & DelSole, 2023). These studies are possibly affected by information leakage from training to the verification samples, typical of the standard use of leave-one-out cross-validation (von Storch & Zwiers, 1999), but link to the AI important goal of identifying and disentangling drivers to supplement incomplete theory. Suarez-Gutierrez et al. (2020) uses Multiple Linear Regression to understand dynamical and thermodynamical contributions to European heat extremes: they use moving threshold definition of extremes to account for the increasing trend, finding atmospheric blocking and soil moisture initial conditions crucial for realistic prediction.

3.2 | Droughts

Drought has wide-ranging impacts on the environment and society, and its risk is expected to increase in a warmer future climate (Chiang et al., 2021; Wilhite, 2000). Skillful drought predictions with sufficient lead time remain a challenge, due to multiple driving factors across different spatial and temporal scales (Hao et al., 2018) and the complex nature of drought. Various indices based on individual or multiple hydro-climatic factors have been developed to meet the need for applications. These include standardized precipitation index (SPI; McKee et al., 1993) and the Palmer drought severity index (PDSI; Palmer, 1965) for meteorological droughts, the Streamflow Drought Index (SDI; Nalbantis & Tsakiris, 2009) for hydrologic droughts, and the SPI including the effect of evapotranspiration (SPEI; Vicente-Serrano et al., 2010) for agricultural applications.

Droughts are primarily triggered by anomalies in hydrologic and meteorological conditions, including precipitation deficit, high temperature, or evapotranspiration. Land–atmosphere interaction and remote processes such as sea surface temperature variations and short-term atmospheric variability (e.g., MJO) also play an important role (Schubert et al., 2007). Furthermore, long-term droughts are associated with the mechanisms that control hydroclimate at multi-year scales, such as decadal ocean variability, deep soil moisture variability, and the impact of climate change and human activities (Esit et al., 2021; Schubert et al., 2007).

While improved weather and climate predictions using AI can potentially enhance drought condition estimations, the verification of these AI approaches focusing on drought events is still lacking. In general, AI in drought prediction involves predicting drought severity using several input data, including hydrometeorological variables and teleconnection indices (Hao et al., 2018).

ANNs often outperform traditional statistical models, such as regression models and autoregressive moving average models, as shown by Poornima and Pushpalatha (2019) in a comparative study. However, their study's test set is only 1 year, and the work fails to provide details about the observational data chosen for verification, therefore its results are

difficult to reproduce. Mokhtarzad et al. (2017) show how complex networks may handle large amounts of nonlinear data-providing SPI and SPEI indices very close to those observed. DL algorithms such as Multi-Layer Perceptrons, LSTM, and CNN have also shown effective performance for drought prediction. Dikshit et al. (2021) uses an LSTM architecture to forecast spatial variations of SPI and SPEI at the subseasonal timescale with promising results, though lacking a proper benchmark. Sahoo et al. (2019) work on a different but related variable, that is the low flow at a gauge station in the Mahanadi River (India). Their LSTM NN, with a very clear separation between training, validation, and test sets, beats the persistence benchmark.

Tree-based models like RF or XGBoost, less prone to overfitting problems, are useful for drought prediction with multiple input predictors. These models effectively process multi-source data such as ground observation, remote sensing data, and climate model output. Rhee and Im (2017) find that tree-based algorithms perform approximately as well as climatology for droughts in South Korea 1–6 months in advance and better than numerical forecasts. Zhang et al. (2019) show that an XGBoost decision tree outperforms a lagged nonlinear model and an ANN for predicting SPEI in central China up to 6 months ahead.

Identifying the most effective ML algorithm for drought prediction is challenging, but the Extreme Learning Machine (ELM) often proves highly skillful. ELM implements a single-hidden layer feedforward neural network, similar to a multi-layer perceptron ANN, and generally provides good generalization performance at a fast-learning speed (Huang et al., 2006). Li et al. (2021) developed three ML models using Random Forest (RF), support vector regression (SVR), and ELM to predict the Standardized Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) with 1- and 3-month lead times, using previous sea surface temperatures (SST) as predictors. These models are tested on four river basins with different climates and frequent droughts (Colorado, Danube, Orange, and Pearl River), and ELM shows the best prediction skill for all of them. Deo and Şahin (2015) compare predictions of the monthly effective drought index in Australia using ELM and conventional ANN, finding that ELM outperformed ANN in predicting drought duration and severity while also demonstrating faster learning and training speeds. Raza et al. (2022) compare ELM's performance in predicting droughts across several weather stations in Pakistan against another ANN, the multi-layer perceptron, and an autoregressive stochastic model. Results show that ELM produced the best drought predictions for nearly all meteorological stations at different forecast times, while also being the most efficient during training and the fastest in generating forecasts. The authors suggest that ELM should be used as an early warning tool for drought forecasting.

More recent studies have suggested combining AI models to take advantage of different algorithms. For instance, CNN merged with RNNs better captures time series dependence (Danandeh Mehr et al., 2022), outperforming all compared ML models for 1-month-ahead drought forecasting. Extensive examples of AI applications in drought prediction are found in AghaKouchak et al. (2022) or Prodhon et al. (2022). A wide range of AI algorithms have shown progress in predicting drought occurrence and related characteristics. However, most studies are geographically limited to areas with available ground data, making generalization complicated. Recent efforts focus on understanding drivers' contribution to drought prediction by applying explainable AI (Dikshit & Pradhan, 2021; Felsche & Ludwig, 2021).

AI has also demonstrated potential in predicting drought impacts. For instance, Sutanto et al. (2019) show that RF can forecast drought-affected sectors such as agriculture, energy, or wildfire with several months' lead time. AghaKouchak et al. (2022) noted that while current studies mainly focus on prediction accuracy, quantifying uncertainties in AI models is needed. This study also suggests using AI as more than just a drought prediction model, proposing it as a tool to discover unknown drought drivers

3.3 | Cyclones and heavy precipitation

Synoptic scale cyclones, both in the tropics and the mid-latitudes, cause considerable economic damage (Mendelsohn et al., 2012) due to associated heavy precipitation, strong winds, and storm surges. Climate change could exacerbate the severity of such extremes, but not necessarily their frequency (Knutson et al., 2020), and predicting their variability on S2D timescales remains challenging (Befort et al., 2022). Heavy precipitation events are not always linked to large-scale weather systems such as cyclones or fronts: many impactful events are instead linked to short-lived, small-scale severe convective events. These extremes are even more challenging for operational climate prediction systems, as their spatial resolution is too coarse to allow the explicit representation of convection. Indeed, numerical climate prediction systems' skill for extreme precipitation substantially decreases beyond a few days in most regions where it has been analyzed (e.g., King et al., 2020; Rivoire et al., 2022).

Characterizing synoptic-scale cyclones is in principle relatively straightforward, as they are associated with macroscopic features in large-scale atmospheric fields such as mean sea level pressure or atmospheric vorticity. Metrics used to describe such extremes range from simple counting to more sophisticated indices aggregating frequency and intensity (e.g., Emanuel, 2005). In contrast, characterizing small-scale heavy precipitation is more sensitive to the method used to define the extreme, for example, exceedance of an absolute value or of a given climatological percentile (Scoccimarro et al., 2013).

AI techniques have been successfully applied to improve the prediction of both cyclones and heavy precipitation events. Examples of ML/DL methods used to predict tropical cyclone (TC) occurrence include CNNs and RFs. RF provides more interpretability on the role of different drivers, and outperforms nonlinear regression models in predicting TCs in the Western North Pacific (Tan et al., 2018). CNN shows higher prediction skill compared to numerical models, particularly when leveraging transfer learning techniques to exploit larger training sets from modeling data (Fu et al., 2023). On the other hand, increased skill from complex architecture often reduces interpretability. de Burgh-Day and Leeuwenburg (2023) propose ablation studies to overcome DL models' interpretability issues while retaining their good skill.

Richman et al. (2017) used SVR to predict the number of seasonal TCs in the North Atlantic and their spatial distribution, outperforming the statistical forecast in place, even if they lack an out-of-sample test. Regression-based approaches have also shown promising results for subseasonal predictions of precipitation (Zhang et al., 2023). A major weakness for localized precipitation extremes is the absence of uniform benchmarking datasets, which hinders the comparison of different methodologies. The representation of precipitation extremes is less reliable in global reanalyses, leading to the choice of localized observational reference datasets, which are often limited to single countries or regions (Scheuerer et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2023). The use of high-resolution, high-frequency global precipitation datasets (e.g., Beck et al., 2017) as a benchmarking standard could improve the robustness of comparisons across studies.

A promising framework for S2D prediction of cyclones is hybrid statistical dynamical predictions. This approach improves the skill of numerical prediction systems in representing weather extremes by finding relationships between large-scale drivers (generally well predicted by dynamical models) and extreme events. It has been applied to precipitation fields, providing probabilistic forecast of precipitation at the subseasonal timescale (Scheuerer et al., 2020). Their ANN/CNN architecture, using predictors from the ECMWF subseasonal forecast, improves forecast of high precipitation accumulation, in week 2, but degrades in weeks 3–4, suggesting the need for additional large-scale predictors.

Several AI applications enhance prediction of climate extremes by improving the way climate forecast model outputs are processed. Polkova et al. (2021) used causal discovery algorithms to understand and improve numerical seasonal forecasts of marine cold air outbreaks, identifying atmospheric circulation patterns and local sea surface temperature as valuable predictors. Applications aimed at improving the representation of wind and precipitation fields exploit DL algorithms trained on high-resolution observations to improve the representation of precipitation (Vosper et al., 2023) or wind patterns (Yang, Zhang, et al., 2022) associated with cyclones, effectively acting as a form of downscaling.

3.4 | Hybrid climate prediction of extremes

Hybrid climate predictions, which combine numerical forecasting techniques with AI methods, have emerged as a promising approach for improving the accuracy and reliability of climate predictions. This approach leverages the physical consistency of dynamical models and the flexibility and adaptability of ML/DL models. This section reviews recent advances in hybrid modeling for predicting weather and climate extremes. We follow the typology developed for hydrological forecasting by Slater et al. (2023) and focus on three main areas: (1) a coupled approach where AI improves the parametrization and initialization of climate models, (2) a serial approach where climate model outputs are post-processed or blended with ML, and (3) a statistical–dynamical approach where climate models are used to train a data-driven model.

The first area addresses the major challenge of accurately representing small-scale processes in climate models, such as cloud formation and convective storms, critical for predicting some types of weather and climate extremes. AI can improve the representation of these processes leading to enhanced predictions of extremes. For instance, Rasp et al. (2018) and Gentine et al. (2018) employ NNs to parametrize convection and cloud processes within the atmospheric column of a climate model. The NNs are trained in multi-scale cloud-resolving simulations to emulate fine-scale modeled processes for coarser-scale forecasts (Figure 2a). Steps towards coupling are also being made for land-surface

FIGURE 2 Schematic representation of methods to combine dynamical models with machine or deep learning to create hybrid predictions.

parametrizations (ElGhawi et al., 2023). Stability of the AI algorithm and generalization to unseen situations are a prerequisite for skillful coupled performance, which is why these algorithms are designed to adhere to known physical relations.

The second area of hybrid prediction uses ML techniques to post-process climate model outputs, correct model bias, and/or downscale model outputs. Statistical models learn systematic biases between forecasts and observations, improving the reliability of extremes' predictions by correcting the probability distribution. For example, errors in model-

generated heavy precipitation are corrected by learning the precipitation patterns induced by ENSO and applying those to forecasted ENSO (perfect prognosis approach; Doss-Gollin et al., 2018, Strazzo et al., 2019, Figure 2b). Systematic errors between forecasts and observations can also be learned with Model Output Statistics algorithms (Figure 2c), where links between predictors and predictands are those of the models (Glahn & Lowry, 1972). Current ML techniques can learn non-linear relations (Haupt et al., 2021; Schulz & Lerch, 2022; Vannitsem et al., 2021) and thus apply corrections depending on the weather conditions in which an extreme is occurring. On subseasonal time scales, studies have employed fully connected NNs (Fan et al., 2023; van Straaten et al., 2023), convolutional and UNet-type NNs (Horat & Lerch, 2023; Scheuerer et al., 2020), RFs (Zhang et al., 2023), regression models (Hwang et al., 2019), and Bayesian methods (Schepen et al., 2014; Specq & Batté, 2020; Strazzo et al., 2019). These post-processing methods produce probabilistic forecasts of weekly, bi-weekly, or monthly accumulated precipitation or average temperature.

Statistical post-processing models can also evaluate the dynamical models they correct, relating error characteristics to the weather circumstances under which they occur, thus expanding the physical understanding of extremes that would be limited by only using numerical models (Mouatadid et al., 2023; Silva et al., 2022; van Straaten et al., 2023).

The third category of hybrid predictions, statistical-dynamical forecasting (Slater et al., 2023) combines dynamical predictions with different empirical, purely data-driven approaches (Figure 2d). One way is to use statistical methods to provide first-guess prediction of important state variables (e.g., NAO) related to the extreme, and then weigh or select dynamical simulations accordingly (Dobrynin et al., 2018; Neddermann et al., 2019; Polkova et al., 2021). The first-guess prediction can be based on expert-informed regression models (Dobrynin et al., 2018), or using causal discovery algorithms (Polkova et al., 2021).

Training a ML model on climate model simulations, and integrating data from large climate model ensembles, is also possible. Known as transfer learning (Figure 2e; Weiss et al., 2016), this approach expands the size of available training sets (Andersson et al., 2021; Gibson et al., 2021; Ham et al., 2019), offering a more statistically robust version of the climate system and its future trends. Combining multiple models or ensemble realizations can further expand the dataset by some orders of magnitude, allowing better generalization under future climate conditions. Additionally, data-driven models based on causal discovery algorithms can be fitted to dynamical simulations to evaluate the presence of known links in the climate system (di Capua et al., 2022).

4 | CHALLENGES IN THE APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE APPROACHES

The vehemence with which AI has irrupted in the climate prediction discussion comes with numerous unresolved challenges that must be addressed to build trust in this emerging technology at the service of climate applications. We identify five major areas of challenges (Figure 3) and propose a few best practices that should be acknowledged and carried out in future studies.

4.1 | Data and processing

Extreme events are rare by definition, and their increasing likelihood in a non-stationary climate (White et al., 2023) poses important scientific challenges for improving climate predictions using AI. In fact, the scarcity of historical data and the absence of unprecedented events in the past, make any statistical approach based on observations prone to failure (Miloshevich et al., 2023). The physical processes driving climate extremes have time cycles ranging from weeks to years, with different seasons exhibiting varying predictive relations. Additionally, many climate variables are temporally correlated at multiple time scales (He et al., 2021), complicating the acquisition of sufficient (effective) samples to learn from. This problem is more pronounced with longer forecast periods, limiting the verification of time-independent forecasts: multi-annual (5–10 years) predictions, whose training sample relies on current atmospheric reanalysis (e.g., ERA5, Hersbach et al., 2020), may only have a dozen samples for training.

As discussed in Section 3, transfer learning can potentially enlarge the learning sample using climate model data, provided relevant processes are realistically represented and model systematic errors are characterized through process-based studies (Eyring et al., 2019). Thus, the climate model selection becomes a crucial part of the pipeline with significant implications for the ML models' final performance. Recent studies have followed various approaches to ameliorate this issue. Some choose a single model that accurately represents the physical processes behind the targeted tasks

Challenges in AI-based Prediction of Climate Extremes

FIGURE 3 The current challenges facing the prediction of climate extremes with AI. Major areas of difficulty (Data and processing, Uncertainty, Interpretability and Causability, Generalizability, and Reproducibility) are shown in black, and accompanied by a complementary icon, while related tasks discussed in the text (Section 4) are shown in white.

(Gibson et al., 2021; Miloshevich et al., 2023), while others pool many models into the training set to capture robust signals (Ham et al., 2019; Ling et al., 2022; Pan et al., 2022). Furthermore, this procedure can be extended by a second training loop, known as fine-tuning, where the ML model is further trained using available observations (Andersson et al., 2021; Ham et al., 2019; Pan et al., 2022), to account for the biases in the first training.

Despite methods to extend the training dataset, the so-called imbalanced learning problem (He & Ma, 2013) is inherent to extreme forecasting. Being rare events, extremes (events in the distribution's tails) result in a large ratio between extreme and nonextreme samples. Imbalanced learning leads to models that are less confident in predicting extreme states resulting in unskilful predictions if not adequately addressed. Proposed solutions often employ resampling techniques, where either the minority class is oversampled or the majority class gets undersampled either through random sampling of the currently available samples (Miloshevich et al., 2023), or by generating new samples using interpolation [Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE); Chawla et al., 2002]. However, re-sampling do not add extra information from the few available extra samples, and some studies point out that resampling may result in unreliable probabilities (Fissler et al., 2022).

Several extreme events are clearly affected by the background global warming trend. An increase in heat wave frequency and magnitude (and the concurrent decrease of cold spells) is occurring virtually everywhere in the world, while heavy precipitation, storm intensity, and drought frequency/duration only locally show increments likely linked to a warming climate. This raises questions on how to handle this anthropogenic constraint to separate its induced predictability from the natural predictability of the system. Many studies simply perform an out-of-sample pre-processing by detrending the training time-series before applying the learning algorithm (e.g., Weirich-Benet et al., 2023). While this approach allows to isolate of natural variability, it excludes a significant source of predictability across multiple timescales (Bellucci et al., 2015; Prodhomme et al., 2022; van Straaten et al., 2023). There is no general solution, and the treatment of trends mostly depends on the specific goals and research questions AI-based predictions are designed for. Improving prediction skills for climate services would benefit from including the trend during learning, while removing it makes sense if the aim is to uncover potential drivers for the studied extreme and separate human-made contribution from natural variability (Zeder & Fischer, 2023). This approach requires an additional choice of trend removal methods (Frankcombe et al., 2015), variables to be detrended, and dealing with variables indirectly affected by

the background trend (e.g., soil moisture). Efforts in this sense have been limited within the ML framework for climate predictions of extremes.

4.2 | Uncertainties

Due to the inherent complexity and chaoticity of the climate system, the relationship between predictors and predictands is intrinsically probabilistic, lacking a one-to-one correspondence. Thus, climate predictions of extreme events are subject to significant uncertainties, particularly aleatoric uncertainties that significantly impact the potential predictability of an extreme event (Lucente et al., 2022). Aleatoric uncertainty can be further split into homoscedastic (invariant to different inputs), and heteroscedastic (varying over different inputs), therefore noisier. This result in over-/under-confident predictions, therefore understanding the statistical properties of the extreme and modeling them accordingly is essential. Likewise, uncertainties in data and ML methods (i.e., epistemic uncertainties) also affect prediction. Hence, probabilistic models are best suited to express the combined uncertainties (Miloshevich et al., 2023; van Straaten et al., 2022), providing a distribution of possible future states that better characterize the nature of the prediction problem. Such distributions are most informative to decision-makers when calibrated, ensuring issued probabilities match observed occurrences (Gneiting et al., 2007). Many ML methods produce probabilistic forecasts, but not all explicit output uncertainty distributions (Luo et al., 2022). Thus, reliable probabilistic ML modeling remains a vital research line in climate prediction of extremes.

Regarding probabilistic approaches, one specific method for ANN is the dropout Monte Carlo approach, during training, a small fraction of neurons are randomly “dropped out” (i.e., deactivated) in each iteration making the trained network more robust (Scher & Messori, 2021). During inference (after training is completed), uncertainty can be quantified by sampling different predictions, each time deactivating random neurons. In contrast, methods like variational autoencoders (VAEs; Kingma & Welling, 2019) or diffusion models (Yang, Lee, et al., 2022), learn the data's underlying probability distribution to sample an ensemble of predictions. Other methods applicable to any ML model train an ensemble of models on data subsets of the data or using different random seeds (e.g., Weyn et al., 2021), or retaining multiple “best estimators” to optimize the hyperparameters. In all these cases uncertainty is treated in a post hoc fashion with no guarantee for calibration.

4.3 | Interpretability and causability

One of the key pitfalls of using AI for predicting climate extremes is the opacity of the model's decision-making process. With few exceptions (e.g., see linear/logistic regression, decision trees, and newly introduced DL; see Agarwal et al., 2021; Barnes et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2019), most ML/DL algorithms are highly complex and non-transparent, making their predictions difficult to interpret. Although high accuracy might be sufficient and interpretability might be less of an issue for some applications (e.g., machine translation or text generation), for high-stakes climate applications and extreme event prediction interpretability is crucial. Trust in the forecast becomes more essential when verification data is limited verification data, as in the S2S/S2D context. There are examples of AI models predicting correctly for the wrong reasons (known as “clever Hans” models; see Lapuschkin et al., 2019). Thus, interpretability becomes fundamental to test against “clever Hans” models and to ensure that the model has learned relevant processes rather than spurious associations.

To address interpretability, the computer science community has developed tools that can be used to explain predictions of black-box AI models in a post-prediction setting, known as eXplainable AI (XAI; Buhrmester et al., 2019; Tjoa & Guan, 2019; Das & Rad, 2020). XAI has attracted attention in numerous fields, including geosciences (e.g., Barnes et al., 2020; Ebert-Uphoff & Hilburn, 2020; McGovern et al., 2019; Toms et al., 2020), by making black box models more transparent, building trust, fine-tuning poor performing models and providing scientific insights (Mamalakis, Barnes, & Ebert, 2022; McGovern et al., 2019). Given the importance of instilling interpretability XAI methods have been successfully applied to forecast climate extremes as well (see Pregon et al., 2022; Salcedo-Sanz et al., 2024; van Straaten et al., 2022).

Despite XAI potential, challenges remain in climate prediction of extremes and geosciences in general. First, XAI tools are imperfect, and their representation of AI models may depend on the application and the prediction setting (Mamalakis, Ebert-Uphoff, & Barnes, 2022). Some studies have pointed out issues with faithfulness to the ML/DL

model, comprehensibility of their results, and reproducibility of the XAI methods (Mamalakis et al., 2022, 2023). Due to these pitfalls, some argue for developing inherently interpretable AI models instead of XAI (Rudin, 2019; Rudin et al., 2022). Even assuming XAI tools are faithful, their insights should only be used to highlight sources of predictability and not to infer causality, as AI models might be using nonphysical relationships (spurious correlations) to make predictions. The limitation in drawing causal conclusions from XAI applications is a significant challenge (Holzinger et al., 2021; Mamalakis, Ebert-Uphoff, & Barnes, 2022; Silva & Keller, 2024). Physics-guided AI (also known as knowledge-guided or physics-informed AI) is a promising approach to impose physical realism in the prediction algorithms and limit spurious correlations during training (Section 5), but this area of research is still in its infancy.

4.4 | Generalizability

Generalizability or generalization refers to the model's ability to make accurate predictions beyond the spatio-temporal boundaries of the training datasets. Traditional ML/DL algorithms assume that training and testing (unseen) data are identically distributed and that relationships between inputs and targets learned during training are valid for testing data. However, in climate science applications, this assumption often fails when models predict extreme values lying outside the climatological distribution of the training data. This out-of-distribution generalization issue can considerably degrade model performance, especially under a warming climate that shifts spatial and temporal distributions of Earth system variables, as current relationships may no longer be valid in the future (D'Amour et al., 2020; O'Gorman & Dwyer, 2018; Rasp et al., 2018). Predicting extreme events across diverse climatic regimes also poses a challenge, as ML/DL model accuracy can vary substantially when applied to contrasting climate zones, such as training in humid regions and predicting in arid ones (Meyer & Pebesma, 2021; O et al., 2020). Therefore, understanding model performance on unseen conditions without labeled data is a fundamental challenge for enhancing the robustness of ML/DL models.

Recent studies show that large and diverse training data from various climate regimes are crucial for robust model performance, even when a model is used over limited geographic regions. AI can infer temporal variabilities of extreme events from contemporary spatial variabilities (space-for-time approach; O et al., 2020; Wi & Steinschneider, 2022). Physics-informed ML/DL also shows a promising step forward for enhancing model robustness (Wi & Steinschneider, 2022). However, out-of-distribution generalization has not been sufficiently explored yet in the context of climate extreme predictions.

4.5 | Reproducibility

Reproducibility refers to the ability of researchers to independently replicate and verify study results given access to data, methods, and procedures employed. This is a minimal prerequisite for ensuring that findings are reliable and trustworthy, particularly in innovative and highly transformative tasks as for ML applications in climate predictions, where new techniques, algorithms, and workflows are published or at an accelerating rate.

However, more than 60% of earth scientists have failed to reproduce other researchers' work, and over 40% could not reproduce their own experiments (Baker, 2016), raising concerns about a "reproducibility crisis" exacerbated in AI literature (Hutson, 2018). A significant issue is the frequent lack of shared source code, due to reasons such as reluctance of disclosing ongoing work, eagerness for competitive advantage, or discomfort with scripting skills (Gundersen & Kjensmo, 2018). Additionally, datasets used for training are often not made available to the community.

Sharing codes and data is crucial, but detailed documentation of the conducted investigation and experiments is equally important. Comprehensive documentation facilitates independent replication of results, increases trust, reduces the effort, and lowers barriers for others to reproduce the experiments. In drafting this review, several papers were excluded because the description of methodology was poor or inaccurate, making the findings questionable.

The scarcity of common datasets and evaluation metrics hinders the intercomparison of climate extreme prediction studies. Benchmarks can make algorithms quantitatively inter-comparable and foster competition. Well-curated benchmark datasets enable collaboration between researchers with different expertise, like climate and computer scientists (Rasp et al., 2020). However, designing standardized datasets is complicated due to the high-dimensional and multi-faceted nature of climate problems (Dueben et al., 2022). Efforts to build benchmark datasets are ongoing for weather-scale forecasts where the atmosphere is still deterministic (WeatherBENCH; Rasp et al., 2020, 2023), or multi-decadal

BOX 1 Best practices to improve trust in AI-based forecast of extremes.

While artificial intelligence provides tools to target potential windows of predictability and eventually improve prediction skill of extreme events, this skill by itself is insufficient. Trust is essential for any early action, which is the ultimate goal of forecasts. Currently, AI-based forecasting generally suffers from a lack of trust for multiple reasons: (1) the exact data processing is often nontransparent and nonreproducible, (2) there are many technical pitfalls that have resulted in exaggerated claims on ML-based skill, and (3) methods are often used as black-boxes with the sources of predictability unexplained.

To overcome this lack of trust, we recommend the following “good practices”:

1. Data, workflows, and analyses should be transparent and easily reproducible across different big-volume datasets. This can technically be achieved by linking open-source software to big climate data platforms, then studies should provide access to the source code, the actual AI model (via appropriate repository, e.g., Github), and exact data used, including preprocessing and postprocessing (on publicly accessible data platforms, e.g., Climate Data Store).
2. Studies should use standardized benchmark datasets and multiple skill-metrics. The use of single and/or uncritical skill metrics (e.g., correlation or area under the ROC curve) can easily lead to inflated skill estimates.
3. Validation should be described step by step, and preferably multiple cross-validation approaches should be tested (Sweet et al., 2023), being aware of the possibility of information leakage from train to test data (Risbey et al., 2021). Ideally, all pre-processing (deseasonalizing, standardizing, etc.) is performed out of sample, though in practice this can be challenging due to lack of independent data samples.
4. Proper and suitable quantification of uncertainties should be prioritized in order to minimize epistemic uncertainties and sample all possible aleatoric uncertainties.
5. An effort in understanding sources of predictability and underlying physical mechanisms is required. Interpreting machine learning models should be a top priority, with interpretability focusing on causality instead of association. Explainable AI can provide insights into the sources of predictability, but a commitment towards interpretable models is highly encouraged (Rudin, 2019).

timescale where the climate response is largely driven by socioeconomic scenarios (ClimateBENCH; Watson-Parris et al., 2022). However, no such benchmarks exist yet for climate predictions, which involve a wide range of process timescales and intricate interactions within and across scales (Box 1).

5 | FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Artificial intelligence has proven powerful to target potential windows of predictability and improve forecast skill at S2D time scale. In the last 5 years, the presence of ML/DL algorithms has exponentially grown in studies targeting the prediction of extreme events weeks and seasons ahead. Evolution and progress in this topic have been extraordinarily quick, and we expect even faster-growing development (Figure 4).

For predictions on inter-annual to decadal time scales, the observational record of rare events provides relatively few independent samples, which impedes robust training and therefore the proliferation of studies on extremes at such a timescale. To be applicable for real-world climate predictions, sufficient useful information must be learned from numerical model simulations (Section 4.1). Applications of such transfer learning implementations include IOD, sea ice, and precipitation seasonal forecasts (Andersson et al., 2021; Gibson et al., 2021; Ling et al., 2022), medium-range weather forecasts (Rasp & Thuerey, 2021), or reconstruction of climate observations (Kadow et al., 2020). Increasing the training sample size is promising for climate predictions of extremes (Miloshevich et al., 2023), especially very rare ones for which only a vast ensemble may cover enough samples.

Recent methods constraining or sub-selecting simulations from large climate model ensembles improved the skill of decadal and multi-decadal climate projections by aligning the phases of internal variability modes with the observed

Perspectives and opportunities for AI-based Prediction of Climate Extremes

FIGURE 4 Perspectives and opportunities in AI-based prediction of extremes.

climate (De Luca et al., 2023; Mahmood et al., 2022). These constraints involve numerous choices, implying sensitivities of the results to specific prediction targets both in space and time. We suggest that ML/DL can be useful to further optimize these methods, for example, by learning the most effective constraining criteria or identifying optimal analogs leading to the genesis of extreme events, to select those simulations providing the highest skill at a specific region and time.

Whether data are representative and comprehensive enough for the ML/DL model to be generalizable and finding the boundary between physical-knowledge and data-learning are major challenges (Balaji, 2021). Discarding the underlying structure of equations seems impossible without incurring in several issues. As learning is only as good as the training data, the resulting NN may not generalize well or violate some basic physics such as the conservation laws. In hydrological modeling, these issues have been addressed by employing an end-to-end hybrid modeling approach based on a ML/DL algorithm constrained by energy (Zhao et al., 2019) or water (Kraft et al., 2022) conservation. Beucler et al. (2021) successfully emulated convective processes using NN while enforcing conservation laws. So-called physics-constrained ML thrived at extracting information in observations while maintaining model interpretability and physical consistency. Ideally, it is possible to venture into learning the fundamental physics by learning the underlying equations for well-known systems (Brunton et al., 2016) and the structure of parameterizations from data, with the advantage of intrinsic interpretability (Zanna & Bolton, 2020). In this context, “learning the physics” means solve closed-form equations for unresolved physics on resolved-scale tendencies, using relations in the data. Resolving the turbulent vertical mixing in the atmospheric boundary layer, for example, may be key to fully understand the atmosphere–land process able to modulate heat waves at subseasonal and seasonal scales.

As pointed out in the sidebar, exploiting the potential of those techniques requires addressing issues related to trust in the AI models. Introducing open-source benchmark datasets can enhance the community's confidence by providing a framework to compare different models on common grounds (O et al., 2020; Mamalakis, Ebert-Uphoff, & Barnes, 2022; see also Section 4.5). Yet, similar examples for climate prediction of extreme events are not available. In particular, introducing a platform to ensure reproducibility according to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable; Wilkinson et al., 2016) approach toward ML applications in weather and climate appears undelayable. The Canonical Workflow Framework for Research (CWFR) has been proposed to ensure the FAIRness and reproducibility of these practices (Mozaffari et al., 2022), targeting data, algorithms, tools, and workflows.

Most AI-based climate prediction models are developed for deterministic predictions, but providing predictions in a probabilistic framework is beneficial for robust estimation of uncertainties and skill improvement. AI-based models offer a larger spectrum of approaches to predict probabilities, but well-calibrated estimates of uncertainties should be ensured, such as introducing perturbations in the initial conditions or creating model ensembles. Calibration can be better achieved when methods are directly trained to output distributions, and when probabilistic loss is used.

Common methods range from distributional regression (networks; e.g., Hu, Ghazvinian, et al., 2023; Schulz & Lerch, 2022), to (implicit) quantile networks (e.g., Bremnes, 2020; Dabney et al., 2018), to histogram-estimation networks (e.g., Scheuerer et al., 2020), or Generalized Linear Models (GLMs) and Generalized Additive Models (GAMs; e.g., Tuel & Martius, 2022).

Numerous unexplored probabilistic ML methods might suit the prediction of climate extremes, like Bayesian NNs (Polson & Sokolov, 2017) or nonparametric models like Gaussian Processes (Rasmussen & Williams, 2005), that have yet not received much attention. Generative models, including Variational Auto Encoders (VAEs; Kingma & Welling, 2019), Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs; Goodfellow, 2016), Normalizing Flows models (Papamakarios et al., 2019), and Diffusion Models (Yang, Lee, et al., 2022), have only very recently been explored for climate predictions of extremes (Spuler et al., 2024), while for weather extremes these techniques have been employed in several applications (Lam et al., 2022; Lessig et al., 2023; Price et al., 2023; Thuemmel et al., 2023). Conformal prediction (Vovk et al., 2005) is another interesting probabilistic approach focusing on distribution-free uncertainty quantification and reliable probabilities, essential to decision-making applications of climate predictions.

While AI research has examined individual extreme events (Section 2), work on predictions of compound extremes is still in its infancy (Zhang et al., 2020). Examples include flooding caused by co-occurrence of high sea level and precipitation, causing substantial runoff in coastal areas (Bevacqua et al., 2019; Wahl et al., 2015); compound hot-dry events linked to persistent anticyclonic weather systems (Bevacqua et al., 2022; De Luca & Donat, 2023; Yin et al., 2023); and heavy precipitation-high wind speed events during cyclonic weather (De Luca et al., 2020; Martius et al., 2016; Zscheischler et al., 2021).

At the time of writing this article, few studies have investigated AI for compound extreme events prediction, particularly at the S2D scale. Park and Lee (2020) assessed coastal flooding as the compound effect of high tides and heavy rainfall in South Korea, developing a future (2030–2080) compound risk map using ML algorithms like k-nearest neighbor, RF, and support vector machine. Sampurno et al. (2022) used a hydrodynamic model trained with similar ML models, to predict compound flooding over the Kapuas River delta (Indonesia) at the weather timescale. In addition, AI-based techniques help quantify relationships between the extremes of two variables (Zhang et al., 2022). Bayesian networks (Sanuy et al., 2020) and ANN (Huang et al., 2021) have been used to understand compound extremes, while complex networks are found capable to drive causal relationships between two or more variables (Sun et al., 2022). In conclusion, scientific knowledge for AI-based skillful predictions of compound extremes exists, and as co-occurrence and interaction of climate extremes often generate more severe socioeconomic impacts (Zscheischler et al., 2018), implementing this knowledge at the S2D timescale may prove useful for planning climate adaptation strategies.

As the community refines AI technologies, we stand to gain invaluable insights to prepare, mitigate, and adapt to climate extremes with greater precision and foresight. The integration of AI into climate prediction of extremes holds immense potential for building more resilient and sustainable societies in the face of an increasingly variable and changing climate.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Stefano Materia: Conceptualization (lead); data curation (equal); funding acquisition (lead); investigation (equal); visualization (equal); writing – original draft (lead). **Lluís Palma García:** Conceptualization (supporting); data curation (equal); investigation (equal); visualization (equal); writing – original draft (supporting). **Chiem van Straaten:** Conceptualization (supporting); data curation (equal); investigation (equal); visualization (equal); writing – original draft (equal). **Sungmin O:** Conceptualization (equal); data curation (equal); investigation (equal); writing – original draft (equal). **Antonios Mamalakis:** Conceptualization (supporting); data curation (equal); investigation (equal); visualization (equal); writing – original draft (equal). **Leone Cavicchia:** Conceptualization (equal); data curation (equal); investigation (equal); writing – original draft (equal). **Dim Coumou:** Conceptualization (equal); supervision (equal); writing – original draft (supporting). **Paolo de Luca:** Conceptualization (supporting); investigation (equal); writing – original draft (supporting). **Marlene Kretschmer:** Conceptualization (equal); data curation (supporting); investigation (equal); writing – original draft (equal). **Markus Donat:** Conceptualization (equal); investigation (equal); supervision (equal); writing – original draft (supporting).

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors have declared no conflicts of interest for this article.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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